

Authenticated Key Exchange in Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks based on Implicit Certificates: Performance Analysis

Bogdan Krivokapic, Slavica Tomovic, *Member, IEEE*, Igor Radusinovic, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract— As the utilization of Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks (UASNs) in industrial and military operations increases, there is a requirement to guarantee the confidentiality and integrity of the data being transmitted. However, protecting communication in UASNs is very challenging as they are often deployed in unattended environments without physical protection. The slow propagation speed of underwater acoustic waves and low channel bandwidth are additional challenges affecting the design and implementation of security mechanisms. This paper outlines the main disadvantages of using conventional key-exchange protocols in resource-constrained environments such as UASNs, and proposes the utilization of implicit certificates and Hashed One-pass Menezes-QuVanstone (HOMQV) key-exchange protocol as an alternative. We implemented the proposed solution on several computing platforms and present the performance evaluation results in terms of computational time and communication overhead. Our analysis shows that using HOMQV in combination with Elliptic Curve Qu-Vanstone (ECQV) protocol for implicit certificate generation can significantly reduce communication and power consumption requirements compared to Diffie-Hellman (DH) protocol based on X.509 certificates.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater acoustic sensor networks (UASNs) are attracting increasing attention from a wide range of industries and scientific communities due to their potential to perform various ocean monitoring and exploration tasks cost-effectively. Many UASN applications require a transfer of confidential data (e.g. military alerts, information about natural resources, etc.), and thus protecting communication is considered a critical issue. Wireless networks, in general, are more vulnerable to security threats than wired networks due to the broadcast nature of communication channels and the high level of mobility and heterogeneity of network nodes. In UASNs, security problems are more pronounced because they are usually left unattended for a long time, and the network nodes are more resource-constrained [1,2]. Furthermore, the underwater acoustic channel is characterized by a slow signal propagation speed (only ~ 1500m/s), low bandwidth, and high attenuation, which results in large communication delays and increased energy consumption. Due to large communication delays, wormhole

attacks can be performed relatively easily by using an out-of-band radio connection above the water surface [3]. On the other side, a low bandwidth makes it difficult to effectively secure the network. Compared to terrestrial wireless sensor networks (WSNs), UASNs require much more energy for data transmission (typically tens of Watts [1]). Hence, there is a significantly higher energy requirement for the same level of network security. For the above-mentioned reasons, most of the security solutions designed for terrestrial networks cannot be directly applied in UASNs [2].

In order to establish a secure communication channel between UASN devices, it is necessary to implement mechanisms for device authentication, data confidentiality, and integrity protection. Symmetric cryptosystems are usually the first choice for confidentiality protection. They assume that a sender and receiver use a common secret key for data encryption/decryption. The key should be updated on regular basis to minimize the risk of exposure. The key distribution can be facilitated with the aid of asymmetric cryptography. However, key exchange algorithms based on asymmetric cryptography typically use X.509 certificates to verify that the public key is associated with a particular entity. The size of these certificates (usually hundreds of bytes [4]), is unacceptably large for UASNs. To address this issue, implicit certificates can be used as an alternative [5-6]. Implicit certificates do not use an explicit digital signature to certify the association between a node's public key and its identity. Instead, a public key is "implicitly" verified by being reconstructed from the data in the certificate.

In this paper, we analyze the suitability of the Elliptic Curve Qu-Vanstone (ECQV) [7] protocol for implicit certificate generation in UASNs. We also present how this protocol can be combined with Hashed One-pass Menezes-QuVanstone (HOMQV) key exchange protocol [8] to provide a secure communication channel between sensor nodes. The protocols are implemented on computing platforms of different capabilities, and their performance has been evaluated in terms of computational overhead and security robustness for different configurations of

cryptographic parameters. In addition, we compared communication overheads of the ECQV-HOMQV key exchange scheme and Diffie-Hellman (DH) key exchange protocol based on X.509 certificates. Our analysis shows that using ECQV and HOMQV protocols significantly reduces bandwidth and power consumption requirements.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II we present the assumed system model and the analyzed security problem. Section III introduces ECQV and HOMQV protocols and explains their advantages and security features. The experimental results are given in Section IV. Section V outlines directions for future work and concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Figure 1 depicts the assumed model of a UASN which consists of a large number of sensor nodes (SNs) deployed underwater. By using acoustic modems, sensor nodes exchange information to cooperatively perform various tasks underwater. They also report the collected data to the sink nodes on the surface periodically. Sink nodes facilitate the transfer of data from the underwater sensor nodes to the shore-side network infrastructure where data processing and analysis are performed. We assume that the sink nodes cooperatively maintain a secure distributed ledger and act as Certificate Authorities (CAs) in the network.

Fig. 1. System architecture.

Enabling secure communication between nodes is crucial for maintaining the integrity and reliability of the collected data. However, due to the broadcasting nature of acoustic communication, data transmitted in plaintext can be easily intercepted, modified, and injected. The potential security breaches include:

- *Man-in-the-Middle attack*: An attacker intercepts and alters the communication between the nodes. The attacker has the ability to read, insert, and modify at will any packet in the communication stream before forwarding the messages to the destination node.
- *Sybil attack*: a single malicious node creates multiple fake identities to send false messages. For example, in the localization process, a Sybil node pretending as a legitimate node can provide false coordinates to the source node.

- *Replay attack*: a valid data transmission is repeated or delayed by an attacker in order to gain unauthorized access or disrupt network communication.
- *Exhaustion attack*: a malicious node floods the network with irrelevant messages, causing network nodes to consume resources and reducing the network lifetime.

In order to protect against these security breaches, it is crucial to have security protocols in place to verify the identity of devices and maintain the confidentiality and integrity of data. To authenticate, devices can exchange certificates that bind their identities with public keys. X.509 certificates are commonly used in terrestrial networks, and they contain important information such as device identity, public key, and an explicit signature of a trusted CA. However, the size of X.509 certificates can be substantial. As an example, when using a 40-byte long ECC public key, OpenSSL [9] generates 864 bytes long X.509 certificate. The certificate increases proportionally with the key size. Since X.509 certificates are unacceptably large for resource-constrained UASNs, the security model evaluated in this paper operates under the premise of using implicit certificates. The implicit certificates certify the relationship between a node's public key and its identity within the same data structure, eliminating the need for an explicit signature. Due to their small size, they are a highly viable option for key exchange in UASNs.

In the rest of the paper, we consider the utilization of the ECQV protocol for implicit certificate generation and HOMQV as a key agreement protocol. Both protocols use a fixed Elliptic Curve with n -th order generator G . Sensor nodes possess two sets of keys, long-term and ephemeral keys. The ECQV protocol is used to obtain long-term keys, which consist of a public key and a private key, represented as (PKU, skU) for a particular node U . Ephemeral keys, on the other hand, are temporary keys generated each time the protocol is executed and are meant to be used only once. For a specific node U , ephemeral public and private keys are represented by KU and kU , respectively. Both types of keys are represented as points on an Elliptic Curve. The protocol also uses a hash function (H) and a Key Derivation Function (KDF) implemented as the SHA-256 hash function. It is assumed that the requestor node knows the public key of the sink (CA) in advance.

III. AUTHENTICATED KEY EXCHANGE PROCEDURE

The key exchange process involves two phases. First, the CA issues an ECQV implicit certificate. Then, the authenticated key exchange is carried out using the HOMQV protocol with the use of the implicit certificate.

A. ECQV protocol

ECQV protocol utilizes complex mathematical properties to link identity information and public keys into certificates. Unlike traditional methods, it does not include the sender's public key in the certificate but instead allows the recipient to calculate it using the sender's certificate and the CA's public key, thereby reducing bandwidth requirement. While implicit certificates have the advantage of being more storage-

efficient, they also have certain disadvantages that limit their usability in resource-unconstrained terrestrial networks that can easily support the exchange of larger amounts of data. However, in UASNs, which have limited resources and communication capabilities, the resource savings may outweigh the increased complexity and decreased flexibility associated with implicit certificates.

Fig. 2. ECQV certificate flow.

The ECQV protocol includes four distinct procedures: a certificate sign request, generation of the certificate, validation of the certificate, and extraction of the public key. These procedures, along with the key agreement protocol, guarantee secure and authentic communication. Fig. 2 depicts the flow of generating the certificate. A sensor node requests a valid certificate from the sink by generating a Certificate Sign Request (*CSR*). The *CSR* contains the node's *ID* and ephemeral public key. The ephemeral key pair is constructed by first selecting the private key as a random positive integer $kU \in [1 \dots n - 1]$ and then computing the related public key as $KU = G \cdot kU$. The ephemeral private key is kept secret in the node's storage. The sent *CSR* is verified by the sink. Once the node's identity is verified, the sink generates the certificate (*CRT*) and a private key contribution r using its long-term key pair ($skCA, PKCA$) and the *CSR*. This process includes several steps, as follows. Sink generates its own ephemeral key pair $KCA = G \cdot kCA$ where $kCA \in [1 \dots n - 1]$. Then it produces the certificate as a point on the Elliptic Curve through the calculation $CRT = KCA + KU$. Optionally, information such as .node *ID* and expiration date can also be added to the certificate. The private key contribution is generated as:

$$r = skCA + H(CRT) \cdot kCA \pmod n \quad (1)$$

After receiving the *CRT* from the CA, the sensor node validates the certificate. Upon successful validation, the node generates the final key pair (skU, PKU) using the *CRT* and r :

$$skU = r + KU \cdot H(CRT) \pmod n \quad (2)$$

$$PKU = skU \cdot G \quad (3)$$

The certificate validation is performed as follows:

$$PKU = skU \cdot G = PKCA + CRT \cdot H(CRT) \quad (4)$$

If all the required steps are completed successfully, a node will be granted a valid certificate that can be used to verify its identity in the network. Other nodes in the network can use equation (4) to determine the node's long-term public key by referencing its certificate and the CA's long-term public key.

Once the ECQV protocol is fully executed, HOMQV protocol is run to establish a secure communication channel.

B. HOMQV protocol

The One-pass HMQV (HOMQV) key exchange protocol [8] is a highly efficient and secure method for authenticating communication. Its one-way design, which involves the sharing of a session key through a single message, makes it especially useful for UASNs as it conserves energy for the sensor nodes. To establish a secure channel towards the other node (or sink) V , a source node U retrieves its *CRT* from storage and sends it, along with its *ID*, to the target node V . The target node then evaluates the *CRT*, extracts the sender's public key PKU based on (4), and generates its ephemeral key pair as $KV = kV \cdot G$, where kV is a random positive integer within the range $[1 \dots n - 1]$. The target node derives the shared key using the *KDF* as follows:

$$SharedKey = KDF(\sigma, ID_U, ID_V, KV) \quad (5)$$

Where ID_U is *ID* of the initiator node, ID_V is *ID* of the target node and σ derived as:

$$\sigma = PKU \cdot (kV + H(KV, ID_U) \cdot skV) \pmod n \quad (6)$$

Finally, node V replies to the node U with its public ephemeral key KV and ID_V . Node U then generates the session key from (5), where σ' is calculated as:

$$\sigma' = skU \cdot (H(KV, ID_U) \cdot PKV + KV) \pmod n \quad (7)$$

The protocol guarantees that both nodes share the same session key by ensuring that $\sigma = \sigma'$.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We implemented the protocols outlined in the previous section on several hardware platforms of different computing capabilities. The performance of the implemented solution is assessed in terms of computation time and communication overhead. We used a lightweight microECC library [11] for efficient computation of elliptic curve operations on resource-constrained devices. The security of the implemented protocols is based on the NP-hardness of the Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP), which is the foundation of many modern cryptographic protocols. The protocols were tested using two security configurations of elliptic curves: SECP160r1 and SECP256k1. The SECP160r1 offers reduced computation time but a lower security level. More precisely, SECP160r1 offers a security level of 80 bits while SECP256k1 offers 128 bits of security. The level of security refers to the number of actions an attacker must undertake to successfully compromise the ECDLP problem. For instance, a security level of 80 bits implies that 2^{80} operations would be needed to break the system. For the sake of performance evaluation, we also implemented a Diffie-Hellman (DH) protocol with X.509 certificates and compared the timings and communication overheads.

The implementation is designed to use software random number generators and does not involve dynamic memory allocation. Additionally, all elliptic curve points used for ephemeral, long-term keys, or certificates are transmitted in a

compressed format to reduce overhead. On the receiving side, these points are uncompressed to affine representation for further usage. The protocols are tested on the following platforms:

- x86_64 PC using DO Intel shared 1 vCPU 1.7Ghz and 512MB RAM
- Arduino Mega 2560 with 8192 MB of SRAM
- RaspberryPi model 2B with a 900MHz quad-core ARM Cortex-A7 CPU and 1GB RAM
- FRDM-KV31F Arm Cortex-M4 120MGz 96 kB SRAM

When it comes to communication overhead, the ECQV-HOMQV key exchange scheme is significantly more efficient than the DH scheme with X.509 certificates (~800B long). In experiments with 10B long IDs, the proposed solution results in a maximum packet size of 30B in the case of SECP160r1 curve, and 42B in the case of SECP256k1 curve. Table 1 and Table 2 provide information on the timings of various cryptographic operations for different curve configurations and platforms. The columns indicate the platforms, while the rows list the cryptographic operations. The operations include: "Cert Request", "Cert Generate," "Cert Extract," and "Cert Validate," which refer to requesting, generating, extracting public keys from certificates using the CA public key, and validating certificates, respectively. Additionally, information on HOMQV operations, as well as operations related to DH with X.509 certificates are provided.

TABLE 1: COMPUTATION TIME (IN MS) WITH SECP160r1 CURVE.

Operation	x86_64	Mega	RPI	M4
Cert Request	0.37	506	1.13	28.3
Cert Generate	0.77	1135	2.67	62.46
Cert Extract	0.37	577	1.24	32.17
Cert Validate	0.74	1117	2.20	61.24
HOMQV receiver	1.19	1890	4.20	118.95
HOMQV sender	0.73	1070	2.44	65.66
X.509 Cert Request	0.43	556	1.23	28.28
X.509 Cert Generate	0.91	1292	3.09	67.21
X.509 Cert Verify	0.51	716	1.62	37.43
X.509 DH receiver	1.36	2135	4.52	128.21
X.509 DH sender	0.81	1174	2.45	69.7

TABLE 2 : COMPUTATION TIME (IN MS) WITH SECP256k1 CURVE.

Operation	x86_64	Mega	RPI	M4
Cert Request	0.73	1733	3.93	59.87
Cert Generate	1.58	3811	8.98	132.02
Cert Extract	0.79	1982	4.48	68.87
Cert Validate	1.48	3775	8.09	130.15
HOMQV CH	2.31	5887	12.67	225.05
HOMQV SN	1.42	3554	7.64	129.54
X.509 Cert Request	0.92	1945	4.41	59.81
X.509 Cert Generate	1.92	4218	9.91	134.25
X.509 Cert Verify	0.99	2324	5.29	71.34
X.509 DH receiver	2.86	6655	14.19	256.63
X.509 DH sender	1.82	3976	8.47	147.46

It can be observed that the most powerful platform can perform all operations within a few milliseconds, while the Arduino Mega takes several seconds to perform the most complex cryptographic operations. As expected, the SECP160r1 curve provides the best timing performance. Compared to DH with X.509 certificates, it is observed that

the combination of ECQV and HOMQV provides around a 10% improvement in timings, with a significantly smaller communication overhead. As we can see, the computation time increases as the security level increases. However, it is important to keep in mind that propagation delays in UASNs are significant (acoustic waves propagate through the water at a speed of around 1500m/s). Considering, that UASN links are typically long-distance, the time needed to ensure secure communication with ECQV and HOMQV is a less pronounced performance issue compared to the propagation delay.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented the performance evaluation of ECQV and HOMQV protocols and examined their potential application for ensuring secure communication in underwater acoustic sensor networks. The protocols are implemented on four different platforms and the timings required to carry out the cryptographic operations are evaluated along with the communication overhead. The results show that the combination of ECQV and HOMQV can provide very high level of security while keeping energy consumption, transmission and processing delay low with small payloads. In our future work, we will resolve some shortcomings of HOMQV protocol such as replay attack vulnerability by employing blockchain technology on sink nodes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper is supported by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060395, Twinning project MONUSEN.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Jiang, "On Securing Underwater Acoustic Networks: A Survey," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 729-752, Firstquarter 2019, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2018.2864127.
- [2] F. Ardizzone et al. "Machine Learning-Based Distributed Authentication of UWAN Nodes with Limited Shared Information," *2022 Sixth Underwater Communications and Networking Conference (UComms)*, Lercio, Italy, 2022, pp. 1-5.
- [3] M. C. Domingo, "Securing underwater wireless communication networks," *IEEE Wireless Commun. Mag.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 22-28, Feb. 2011.
- [4] Chiara Petrioli, et al. "Feasibility Study for Authenticated Key Exchange Protocols on Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks", *Proc. of the 14th International Conference on Underwater Networks & Systems (WUWNet '19)*, pp. 1-5, 2020.
- [5] C. -S. Park, "A Secure and Efficient ECQV Implicit Certificate Issuance Protocol for the Internet of Things Applications," in *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 2215-2223, 1 April, 2017.
- [6] Duy An Ha, et al. "Efficient authentication of resource-constrained IoT devices based on ECQV implicit certificates and datagram transport layer security protocol", *Proc. of the 7th Symp. on Information and Communication Technology*, New York, USA, 173-179. 2016.
- [7] Certicom Research, "SEC 4: Elliptic Curve Qu-Vanstone Implicit Certificate Scheme (ECQV)," *Standard for Efficient Cryptography*, Jan. 2013.
- [8] Shai Halevi and Hugo Krawczyk, "One-pass hmqv and asymmetric key-wrapping", In *International Workshop on Public Key Cryptography*, pp. 317-334. Springer, 2011.
- [9] OpenSSL library: <https://www.openssl.org/>, Last visited Jan. 2023.
- [10] K. MacKay, "MicroECC," <https://github.com/kmackay/micro-ecc>, Last visited Jan. 2023.